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Analysis of Interest in Forming Cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta

Shinta Heru Satoto¹, Hasa Nurrohim KP², C Ambar Pujiharjanto³

^{1,2,3} Faculty of Business and Economic, UPN “Veteran” Yogyakarta

Correspondence: Hasa Nurrohim KP, Faculty of Business and Economic, UPN “Veteran” Yogyakarta.
Email: hasa.nurrohim@gmail.com

Abstract

This research was conducted to help the people of Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta to overcome the problems they face regarding the management of funds originating from fees charged to residents for the use of clean water. The formation of cooperatives is one of the solutions that is considered appropriate for this problem, so research is carried out on the influence of the factors that influence interest in forming cooperatives in the Village. The results showed that knowledge of cooperatives, subjective norms, and behavioral control influenced the interest of the Kayoman Village community to form cooperatives. While the attitude does not affect the interest in the formation of cooperatives.

Keywords: Knowledge of Cooperatives, Subjective Norms, Behavioral Control, Attitude

1. Introduction

Economic development is one step that can be taken to achieve social welfare. Economic development shows a process of change towards improvement that is carried out consciously and planned to be able to increase the standard of living of the community. In general, economic development is used to describe changes in the economy within a country that involve both qualitative and quantitative improvements. Economic development is said to be successful if there is a continuous process of change, there is an increase in income in the long term, and there is a change in the economic structure. In this economic development, the community will act as the main actor and the government will act as a supporter.

Cooperatives are a suitable platform for economic development in Indonesia. Cooperatives can help develop the economic potential and capabilities of their members to improve the economic and social welfare of the community. In rural areas, village cooperatives are needed to support government development programs in the economic sector. Growing village cooperatives and awareness of cooperatives among the community, especially

youth, is still very much needed due to the lack of knowledge of the village community about the importance of cooperatives.

Interest in cooperatives is an important factor that influences the formation of a cooperative. Interest in cooperatives can be manifested by feeling happy to join cooperative members voluntarily, willing to take advantage of cooperative services, willing to make purchases at cooperatives, paying attention to the development of cooperatives, and having awareness and willingness to be involved in every cooperative activity. If someone already has a high interest in cooperatives then that person will be willing to participate actively in forming and promoting cooperatives. Interest is strongly influenced by various factors, including the learning process (Putra, 2014); attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral control (Jayanegara, et al., 2020); perception and motivation (Pangestuti, 2016, Yanti, 2020, Alamsyah, 2021), cooperative knowledge (Jaya, et al., 2019), and cooperative behavior (Fatmawati, et al., 2019).

Kayoman Village is a village located in Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta. For years, Kayoman Village has experienced problems in the supply of clean water. Since 2017, residents and the village government have overcome this problem by building drilled wells as a source of clean water for the community. Residents who need clean water can get it by paying a certain fee to get clean water from drilled wells. In its development, the village government needs a forum for managing funds originating from fees charged to residents for the use of clean water. The role of cooperatives is quite important so that the funds collected can be managed properly and can be used to improve the welfare of the village community. In addition, it is hoped that with the formation of cooperatives, the development of business groups in Kayoman Village, which so far have been in the form of household businesses, can open up and create wider employment opportunities. It is also hoped that the development of this business group will improve with the existence of cooperatives, both in terms of increasing income, managing ability, and contributing to the economy of families and surrounding communities.

This study seeks to analyze the factors that influence interest in forming cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta as an initial effort to pioneer the formation of cooperatives in Kayoman Village. It is hoped that by knowing the factors that influence people's interest in forming cooperatives, people will be encouraged to actively participate in the process of establishing and developing cooperatives in the future.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Interest in Cooperative

Interest in cooperatives is a high desire that is manifested in feelings of pleasure, attention, concentration, awareness, and a willingness to be involved in cooperative activities (Catur and Setiawina, 2018). Interest in cooperatives consists of indicators of feeling happy in cooperatives, attention to cooperatives, concentration on cooperative activities, awareness of cooperatives, willingness to participate in cooperative activities, and involvement in cooperative activities.

One's interest in cooperating is a basic determinant related to personal factors and social influence. Personal factors that determine interest in cooperatives are in the form of feelings of pleasure or displeasure towards cooperatives, awareness of cooperatives, attention, and willingness to cooperate efforts. Meanwhile, subjective norms relate to one's perception or view of social pressure (other beliefs) which will affect the intention to do or not to do the behavior being considered (Jogiyanto, 2007:31-32).

2.2 Cooperative Knowledge

UU no. 25 of 1992 concerning cooperatives, mentions various knowledge about cooperatives, including cooperative business entities, cooperative foundations, goals, benefits, and cooperative principles. Cooperative knowledge possessed by a person will determine the success of the course of a cooperative. According to Widiyanti (2002: 74), the success of cooperatives in achieving their goals will largely be determined by the knowledge,

appreciation, and awareness of the cooperative members. By knowing the life of cooperatives, a person will have the awareness to be able to participate actively, and cooperative efforts will be able to progress and develop so that cooperative success is achieved.

Hypothesis 1: Knowledge of cooperatives has a positive effect on interest in forming cooperatives

2.3 Attitude

Attitude is an action that tends to be obtained from learning outcomes with consistent intentions, which shows a feeling of liking or disliking an object. (Schiffman, and Kanuk, 2008). This relates to one's beliefs about the consequences arising from behavior. According to Fishbein and Ajzen (1991), attitudes in behavior are determined by (a) behavioral beliefs (*Behavioral Belief*), namely the belief that behavior will produce an output or belief in the existence of consequences for carrying out certain behaviors, and (b) evaluation of consequences (*Outcomes Evaluation / Evaluation of the Consequences*), namely one's evaluation of the output or evaluation of the consequences of behavioral beliefs.

In cooperatives, attitudes towards the formation of cooperatives indicate the extent to which individuals have favorable or unfavorable evaluations of the existence of cooperatives in the form of several beliefs one has about the consequences of forming cooperatives and subjective evaluations of these consequences. The convenience and benefits obtained by the existence of cooperatives will make the interest in forming cooperatives continue to grow. People will assume that the existence of cooperatives will provide many benefits for society. Thus, the formation of cooperatives is seen as a positive thing for the welfare of society in the future.

Hypothesis 2: Attitude has a positive effect on interest in forming cooperatives

2.4 Subjective Norm

Subjective norm is the extent to which a person has the motivation to follow other people's views on the behavior he will do (Ajzen, 2007). Subjective norms are formed by normative beliefs (*normative belief*), and motivation to comply (*motivation to comply*). Normative beliefs are beliefs about other people (reference groups or references) that they think what should be done or not done; or beliefs about other people's expectations (reference group) of him about what should be done. Meanwhile, compliance motivation is motivation that is in line with normative beliefs or motivation that is in line with the people who are the reference group (Angelina and Japarianto, 2014). In cooperatives, belief in the existence of cooperatives can come from parents, close friends, co-workers, and so on.

Hypothesis 3: Subjective norms have a positive effect on interest in forming cooperatives

2.5 Behavioral Control

Behavioral control is the ease or difficulty of perception to perform behavior (Ajzen, 2007). Behavioral control is shaped by control beliefs (*control belief*), namely the probability that several factors support an action/behavior, and the strength of the controlling factor (*power of control factor/access to the control factor*), namely subject access or subject power related to the factors that support the behavior. (Angelina and Japarianto, 2014).

In cooperatives, behavioral control will be related to people who have the desire to make changes or do something different for the sake of the common interest and will be encouraged to achieve these goals. The belief that the establishment of cooperatives in an area will be a driving force to change life in a better direction, will encourage someone's interest in supporting the establishment of cooperatives.

Hypothesis 4: Behavioral control has a positive effect on interest in forming cooperatives

3. Research Methods

3.1 Population and Research Sample

The population in this study is the people of Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta, where cooperatives have not been formed in this area and face problems that can be solved by having

cooperatives. The research sample is part of the people of Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta. The data collection method is by distributing questionnaires directly. Questionnaires will be distributed in a structured manner in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta.

3.2 Variable Measurement

The variables used in this research are interest in cooperatives (as independent variables), and the 4 dependent variables are cooperative knowledge, attitudes, subjective norms, and behavior control. The data were obtained by distributing questionnaires consisting of 25 question items, which consisted of 5 variable interest in cooperating question items; 7 items of cooperative knowledge variable questions, 5 attitude variable question items; 5 items of subjective norm variable questions; and 3 question items for behavioral control variables.

Variable measurements were carried out using a Likert scale. Meanwhile, the instrument test was carried out by testing the validity and reliability. Test validity is used to measure the level of validity or validity of an instrument. A reliability test is used to measure the accuracy of measuring instruments.

4. Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis was performed using multiple regression analysis with the following regression equation:

$$Y = a_0 + a_1 \text{Knowledge} + a_2 \text{Attitude} + a_3 \text{Norm} + a_4 \text{Behavioral} + e$$

To prove hypotheses 1, 2, 3, and 4, it is expected that the regression coefficient is $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3,$ and α_4 significant at a specified level of significance (1%, 5%, or 10%). This shows that knowledge, attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral control influence the interest in forming cooperatives.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 1 shows the characteristics of the respondents based on age and education. 4.5% of respondents aged < 30 years, 72% of respondents aged 30-50 years, and 23.5% of respondents aged > 50 years. Based on education level, 21% of respondents had elementary school education; 15% of respondents had junior high school education; 46% of respondents had high school education; 1% Diploma 1 person, and 18% of respondents with undergraduate education.

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age and Education

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 30 years	3	4,5%
30 – 50 years	49	72%
> 50 years	16	23,5%
Total	68	100%
Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Elementary School	14	21%
Junior High School	10	15%
Senior High School	31	46%
Diploma	1	1%
Masters	12	18%
Total	68	100%

5.2 Instrument Test Results

Validity test results show that all the significance values of the question items are less than or equal to 0.05. So it was concluded that all question items with cooperative knowledge variables, attitudes, subjective norms, behavioral control, and interest in forming cooperatives can be declared valid. The results of the reliability test show that the value *Cronbach Alpha* all variables greater than 0.70. Thus, it can be concluded that the variables of cooperative knowledge, attitudes, subjective norms, behavioral control, and interest in forming cooperatives can be declared reliable, and testing can be continued.

5.3 Research result

The test results using multiple linear regression in Table 2 show that the variables of cooperative knowledge, subjective norms, and behavioral control show a significance value of less than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the variable knowledge of cooperatives, subjective norms, and behavioral control have a significant effect on interest in cooperatives. While the attitude variable shows a significant value of 0.927 greater than 5%, it is concluded that the attitude variable does not affect the interest in cooperating.

Table 2: Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	Beta	t	Say.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	.593	.537		1.106	.273
X1	.873	.254	.602	3.435	.001
x2	.015	.164	.013	.092	.927
X3	-.406	.201	-.322	-2.015	.048
X4	.429	.123	.434	3.499	.001

5.4 Discussion

Knowledge of cooperatives has a significant influence on interest in cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency. This shows that respondents who have good knowledge of cooperatives will show a high interest in the formation of cooperatives in Kayoman Village. Respondent's knowledge of cooperatives, in this case, is related to knowledge of cooperative objectives, functions, and roles of cooperatives, rights and obligations of cooperative members, cooperative principles, cooperative principles, and cooperative organizational instruments. With this understanding, respondents will participate and take advantage of the existence of cooperatives to improve shared welfare. This shows that knowledge of cooperatives is the main key for someone to become a member of a cooperative. The better one's cooperative knowledge, the higher one's interest in forming cooperatives.

Attitudes indicate the extent to which individuals have beliefs about the consequences of forming cooperatives and subjective evaluations of these consequences. The results showed that attitude did not affect interest in forming cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta. This means that the belief in the existence of cooperatives, the benefits of cooperatives, and the benefits obtained do not affect interest in forming cooperatives. The people of Kayoman Village view that the formation of a cooperative is something new that is expected to have a better impact on their lives, so there is not much thought and evaluation of the consequences of forming a cooperative which is taken into consideration for the formation of a cooperative in their Village.

Subjective norms have a significant influence on the interest in forming cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta. Subjective norms indicate individual perceptions about whether other people will support or not realize the action (Baron & Byrne, 2003). In the interest of forming cooperatives, suggestions from family, friends, co-workers, the opinions of other people who are known, and important people around, have a positive influence on interest in forming cooperatives. The community views that

other people's favorable views of the existence of cooperatives will influence their interest in joining as members of cooperatives. The better the support from others, the higher the interest in forming cooperatives.

Behavioral control has a positive effect on interest in forming cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta. Behavior control shows a person's perception of obstacles in carrying out a behavior. In the interest of forming a cooperative, the people of Dusun Kayoman have hope that with the existence of a cooperative, life will be better in the future. In addition, the community has confidence that it will be easy for them to join as cooperative members.

The higher the community's confidence in the convenience and welfare that will be obtained, the greater the community's interest in the formation of cooperatives.

The cooperative knowledge variable is the most powerful factor influencing interest in forming cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari District, Gunungkidul Regency, Yogyakarta. While the attitude variable has the smallest effect compared to other independent variables. The finding that the cooperative knowledge variable has the strongest influence on interest in forming cooperatives, indicates that the community has sufficient knowledge about cooperatives, especially those related to cooperatives. cooperative objectives, functions, and roles of cooperatives, rights and obligations of cooperative members, cooperative principles, cooperative principles, and cooperative organizational instruments. In addition, the community seems to have hope that with the formation of cooperatives, the development of business groups in the Kayoman Village, which so far have been in the form of household businesses, can be further enhanced by the existence of cooperatives, both in terms of opening up job opportunities, increasing income, managing ability and contributing to the economy. family and the surrounding community.

5.5 Implications of Research Results

Based on the findings in this study, the theoretical implications that can be conveyed are that cooperative knowledge, subjective norms, and behavioral control have a positive and significant effect on the interest in forming cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari, Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta. The results of this study enrich empirical studies and clarify the relationship between the concept of cooperative knowledge, subjective norms, and behavioral control, which have a positive and significant effect on interest in forming cooperatives. As an effort to support the community's positive attitude towards the interest in forming cooperatives, the local government needs to start pioneering and prepare itself to realize the formation of cooperatives in the Village. The local government can assist people who already have activities or businesses that still need to be fostered to increase their capacity. The method of mentoring activities can be in the form of management assistance, technical/production assistance, or both. The involvement and support of the local government is needed to encourage the immediate formation of cooperatives.

6. Conclusion

Interest in cooperatives is an important factor that influences the formation of a cooperative. In this study, cooperative knowledge, subjective norms, and behavioral control have a positive influence on the interest in forming cooperatives in Kayoman Village, Gedangsari, Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta. This shows that the people of Kayoman Village have a fairly high interest in forming a cooperative which is expected to be able to solve the problems they face and can help improve the welfare of the surrounding community.

Knowledge of cooperatives that has the strongest influence indicates that the community has good knowledge of cooperatives. Communities are quite aware of the benefits and advantages of forming cooperatives. Most of the respondents who have a higher education indicate that the community is quite mature and ready for the existence of cooperatives. So that the local government can start efforts to realize the formation of cooperatives in the village.

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